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БЕОГРАД

ФИЛОЗОФСКИ ФАКУЛТЕТ
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БАЊА ЛУКА

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ON THE MACEDONIAN LITERARY LANGUAGE AND ITS DIALECTAL BASE*

Savremeni makedonski jezik se razvio na bazi onih dijalekata koji su zahvatili najjužnije južnoslovenske oblasti. U isto vreme, makedonski dijalekti sačuvali su čvrste organske veze sa susednim južnoslovenskim jezicima, bugarskim i srpskim. Ipak, kodifikacija makedonskog jezičkog standarda, koja je u odnosu na druge slovenske jezike došla prilično kasno, istakla je potrebu da se makedonski standard gradi na onom makedonskom dijalektu koji je dovoljno udaljen od bugarskog i srpskog jezika. Već od 19. veka kao osnovni nosilac jezičkog i uopšte kulturnog saobraćaja u Makedoniji nameće se tzv. centralni makedonski dijalekat.

Ključne reči: Makedonski jezički standard, makedonski dijalekti, centralni dijalekat, balkanizmi, migracije, bugarski dijalekti, srpski dijalekti.

The Macedonian literary language is spoken in the Republic of Macedonia, one of the six republics of former S.F.R. Yugoslavia. This standard language was created in the middle of the 20th century, at the end of World War II. Hence, the Macedonian literary language has become one of the youngest members of the family of Slavic literary languages. Historical circumstances did not allow an earlier codification of the Macedonian standard. Ironically, the Macedonian territory where the first Slavic literary language had been founded in the 9th century, the so-called Old Church Slavic language, was the last one to obtain a literary language in the modern sense of meaning.

The Macedonian language has developed among the Slavs that settled to the south from other Slavic tribes. In spite of that, the Macedonian dialects still

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keep many features that connect the Macedonian area with the neighbouring Slavic languages – Bulgarian and Serbian. In addition, these contact zones have been, through history, areas of irradiation of various political and cultural influences which are reflected in the Macedonian language. The present-day distribution of Macedonian dialects confirms these relations. The southeastern Macedonian dialects, which cross the Macedonian-Bulgarian border, in many linguistic features realize a natural link to the southwest Bulgarian dialects. The dialectal type situated in the north of the Republic of Macedonia is, in fact, part of the south-Serbian dialectal complex. On the other hand, far from these influences, in the central part of Macedonia (Prilep – Bitola – Veles) a typical Macedonian dialect has been formed.¹

I.

It was as early as the middle of the 19th century that the Macedonian intellectuals started pointing at the specific Macedonian linguistic features. **Partenie Zografski**, for example, a man of broad philological education, in his article titled “Thinking about the Bulgarian Language” numbered a dozen typical Macedonian linguistic features (see: Документи... I, 1981: 187-190). His aim was to point at the features which just distinguish Macedonian from Bulgarian. Among these features Zografski included:

- full pronunciation of the vowels *e* and *o* (without reductions which are typical of Bulgarian);
- vowel *e* as a continuant of Common Slavic *jat* (instead of Bulgarian *-el/-ja*);
- vowel *a* (“clear *a*”) as a continuant of Common Slavic nasal *o* (*рака, мака, каде*, - instead of Bulgarian *ѣ*);
- omission of the consonant *h* (*оро, убаво, одеа*), or its substitution with *v*/*f* (*уво, праф, читаф*, - instead of Bulgarian *h*), etc.

At the beginning of the 20th century, **Krste Misirkov**, the famous reformer and codificator of the Macedonian literary language, in his book “On the Macedonian Affairs” (Sofia 1903) recommends the central Macedonian dialect as a basis for the future standard language. According to Misirkov, this dialect shows “equal distance” to Bulgarian and Serbian (Misirkov 1903: 145). As a representative linguistic feature Misirkov also stressed the *a*-reflex of the old nasal *o*. Thus, wrote Misirkov, in the central zone there is *рака* (‘hand’) in the eastern dialects *ръка*, in the northern *рука*, and in the western and southern *рока* and *ронка* respectively.

Wide-range dialectological research in the Republic of Macedonia after World War II has confirmed the existence of many specific dialectal features, especially in

¹ As a special part of the western dialect there is a narrow peripheral zone located along the Albanian and southwestern Serbian borders.

western Macedonia where the so-called central Macedonian dialect (Skopje – Veles – Prilep – Bitola; Kičevo – Poreče) is situated. The prominent Macedonian dialectologist **Božidar Vidoeski** has pointed at a spectrum of significant linguistic features in this Macedonian zone (Видоески 1984), such as:

- vowel *a* as a continuant of the old nasal vowel *o* (*рака, пат*);
- sequence *ol* as a continuant of the old vocallic *l* (*волна, долго, солза*);
- the syllabic function of the consonant *r* (*врџ, врџот, дрво*);
- a five-vowel system (*i, e, u, o, a + r voc.*);
- a wide spread of consonants *κ* ' and *g* ', and pairs of consonants *č* : *dž, ts* : *dz*;
- a tendency to neutralize the palatal consonants correlative (*ключ, недела*);
- the 3rd person plural ending *-at* in the present tense (*викаат, носат*);
- the 3rd person plural ending *-a* in the aorist and imperfect (*дојдоа, викаа, носеа*).

Unlike the Bulgarian linguists (see: III), the Serbian linguists very early inclined to accept distinctive traits of the Macedonian linguistic area. Even between the two world wars, when Vardar Macedonia (nowadays the Republic of Macedonia) used to belong to the Kingdom of Serbia and subsequently to the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, - Serbian dialectologist **Aleksandar Belić**, who generally regarded the Macedonian zone as part of Serbian dialects, accepted that the Macedonian western dialect, nevertheless, “has its own special features”, and that it is “far distanced” from both the Bulgarian and Serbian dialectal centers (Белић 1935: 31, 74).²

Regarding the Macedonian position among southern Slavic dialects **Pavle Ivić** wrote about the bulk of the Macedonian territory which is separated from the neighbouring languages and dialects. In this sense, the main position again belongs to the central Macedonian dialect (Ivić 1973: 27). These linguistic features are striking especially when this dialect is compared with those south Slavic dialects which have furnished the bases of Bulgarian and Serbian literary languages. These differences are outstanding especially on the phonological level:

Common Slavic	ь	ъ	ѣ	nas. e	nas. o	voc. l
East Bulgarian	e	ə	'a / e	e	ə	lə / əl
Central Macedonian	e	o	e	e	a	ol
Serbian (New Štokavian)	a	a	e/(i)je	e	u	u

² At the end of World War II, as eminent Serbian linguist, Aleksandar Belić took part in the processes of codification of the Macedonian literary language (Радић 2003).

Of course, in the contact zones of Macedonian, Bulgarian and Serbian, linguistic differences are smaller. The central Macedonian area is in contact with two Bulgarian dialects in the east (areas of Rodopi and Čustendil), with one Macedonian dialect in the south (south Macedonian), and one Serbian dialect in the north (Svrljig-Lužnica dialect, see footnote 3). Towards the southern Macedonian dialect and towards the Bulgarian Čustendil dialect there are no so strong dialectal borders, as those towards the Bulgarian Rodopian dialect and the Serbian dialect of Svrljig-Lužnica (Ivić 1973: 28):

Common Slavic	ь	ъ	ѣ	nas. e	nas. o	voc. l
Rodopi	'ə	ə	a ^o	'ə	ə	lə / əl
Čustendil	e	a	e	e	a	lə / əl
South Macedonia	e	o	e	e	ə	l
Svrljig-Lužnica	ə	ə	e	e	u	lə / u

In a certain respect these differences are also smaller between the Macedonian literary language (the central dialectal base) and the neighbouring dialects, which is due to natural tendencies of literary languages to include some features from dialects which don't belong to the area of dialectal base of the literary language. The Macedonian literary language, for example, contains some linguistic features from the eastern Macedonian dialect (Конески 1981: 62-69).

II.

In the wide area of southern Slavic languages there are two main branches of languages. The eastern branch consists of the Bulgarian and Macedonian languages, while the western branch comprises Serbo-Croat and Slovenian. There is a well-known linguistic border which divides these groups of languages, and this linguistic border, of course, does not follow the state borders.³ But this, as well as other linguistic traits shows that the Central Macedonian zone does not belong entirely to the Eastern group of South Slavic languages, and that the linguistic

³ For example, the northern dialect of Macedonia (Tetovo – Kumanovo – Kratovo), with dominant Serbian features, belongs to the western group of South Slavic languages (Serbian Svrljig-Lužnica dialect). Hence, the yers in strong positions have yielded one reflex (e.g. сын, дън), the nasal vowel *o* has become *u* (рука, пут), palatals *l'* and *n'* have been preserved (пале, њива), the feminine noun ending in plural is *-e* (жене, њиве), pronouns and adjectives end in *-ga* (њезга, свакога), in the present tense there is the ending *-to* in the 1st person plural (знамо, идемо), in word formation there are suffixes *-ic* and *-oča* (нетлић, чистоћа) etc. (Видоески 1998: 95-104). These features are not typical of Macedonian and Bulgarian linguistic zones.

border in its southern zone, between Macedonian and western part of South Slavic languages, is more flexible. That is why some linguists also point at a gradual dialectal transition between Serbian and Macedonian, which includes a high degree of mutual intelligibility within these zones (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...).⁴ Blaže Koneski, the famous Macedonian linguist, wrote that “the Macedonian dialects have been a part of the continuum of Serbian and Bulgarian dialects for so long, that today it is not possible to draw distinct boundaries between them” (*Koneski*: www.mymacedonia.net...). Therefore, there are no linguistic reasons to link Macedonian either with one side only, or to view Macedonian territory as part of the Bulgarian dialectal complex. Even Antoine Meillet, the well known linguist comparatist, wrote that Macedonian and Bulgarian dialects had developed a great difference between them (Meje 1965: 40). Why has this happened?

a) First, from the beginning the Macedonian zone was far distanced from the central parts of the Bulgarian language and from the direct Bulgarian political influences for a long period. This has enabled the Macedonian language to develop and preserve a series of significant linguistic features (see: I). At the same time, the Macedonian language was developing in specific historical circumstances, in a region of manifestly strong contact among the various Balkan languages. The well known Swiss linguist, Ferdinand de Saussure, the founder of linguistic as a modern science, wrote that in Macedonia many languages had been spoken, “Turkish, Bulgarian, Serbian, Greek, Albanian, Aromanian, etc., mixed in different ways from district to district” (Sosir 1996 [1915]: 192). Aromanian and Albanian influences have been especially strong in some parts of Macedonian territory into this day. Although the Macedonian, Bulgarian and some parts of Serbian dialects share many Balkan linguistic features, the so-called Balkanisms,⁵ owing to its position the Macedonian language has developed some Balkanisms of its own, which are not known to the Bulgarian and Serbian dialects. These Balkan characteristic were spread mostly in western Macedonia, in different linguistic levels:

- in the temporal system (e.g. the analytic perfect tense with the auxiliary verb “have”: *имам читано, имав читано*; see: Goľab 1959: 416-421);
- in word order and structure of the sentence (e.g. with enclitics at the beginning of the sentence: *те сакам, го гледам, сум болен*; see: Настев 1988: 73-75);

⁴ Therefore, there was a notice in one of the grammar books that in Yugoslavia Serbo-Croat “differs considerably from the language of Slovenia, in the north-west, and to a lesser extent from that in Macedonia, in the south-east” (Javarck-Sudjić 1978: XI). Some linguistic levels show this very well (see: Радич 1993).

⁵ Unlike other Slavic languages, the case system is almost entirely lost, adjectives are compared by using separate prefixes for the comparative and superlative, the infinitive form does not exist any more, etc.

- in word formation (e.g. the diminutive suffix *-ule*: *детуле, пилуле, човечуле*; see: Koneski, Vidoeski, Jašar-Nasteva 1968: 523, 528), etc.

These features have secured the Macedonian language a special position among Balkan Slavic languages and due to that in modern linguistics literary Macedonian is usually viewed as the most balkanized South Slavic language (Илиевски 1988: 13-35). Of course, these Balkan language features have found their place in the contemporary Macedonian literary language too, and just because of that it has made another important difference to the Bulgarian literary language.⁶

b) Geographically, Macedonian territory is especially by the way of the Vardar-Morava valley wide open towards the north.⁷ This fact can explain many linguistic phenomena within the framework of the Serbian-Macedonian relationship. It can explain some very old Macedonian linguistic features preserved in a series of South Serbian toponyms, as well as many Balkanisms which spread mostly from the Macedonian territory to the central parts of Serbia till today, and which have great influence even on the contemporary Serbian literary language (Радић 2003а: 130-145, Радић, 2003). On the other hand, it can also explain not only the Serbian nature of the northern (Slavic) dialect of the Republic of Macedonia, on whose border the Macedonian capital Skopje is situated, - but also the series of linguistic features which spread from Serbian and north Macedonian territory through all over Vardar Macedonia, as early as the middle ages.⁸ It was probably owing to these influences that in a major part of central Macedonia the ekavian reflex of the old vowel 'jat' (see: I), and affricates *k'* (Maced. *ќ*) and *g'* (Maced. *џ*) as continuants of Common Slavic consonant groups **tj*, **dj* have to spread or strengthened. A reduced extent of palatal-velar consonant opposition in the central Macedonian dialect links this zone to the Serbian dialects, too (Белић 1935: 34-52, Ивић 1985²:

⁶ In the Macedonian literary language stress is placed on the first syllable of bisyllabic words and on the antepenult in words of three or more syllables, definite nouns are indicated by a set of three definite suffixal articles (type: *-ов, -от, -он*), etc.

⁷ There are some indications which show that contacts between Macedonian and Serbian also used to exist in the zone of present-day north Albania. Some linguistic data suggest that Slavic dialects from Western Macedonia were in a direct contact with Serbian dialects from southeastern Montenegro until the beginning of the period of Ottoman rule (Радић 1993).

⁸ Some new texts have it that after Macedonian linguistic codification Serbian "and local dialect forms continue to exert an influence on the language, especially those in the Western dialect area, which is the basis for the standard" (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...). Perhaps, we could talk, before all, about influences which directly enter from the Serbian dialectal type of the Skopje region ("local dialect forms"), as the capital, into Macedonian literary language (and indirectly into the "Western dialects area"), and after that, in the second place, about influences of "Serbo-Croatian", as the principal language of the former Yugoslavia. Naturally, after the disintegration of the S.F.R. Yugoslavia the first type of influences have continued to exist with the same intensity. It is well shown in some recent Macedonian texts where even an aversion to this dialect is expressed (Спировски 2002: 64). On the other hand, a cultural influence from Serbia could not be definitely stopped after Macedonian separation either (see footnote 13).

16-21, see also: Alexander 2000, maps 5, 13). From this point of view it may be clear why the Macedonian Đorđi Puljevski wrote in the 19th century that the Bulgarian language is close to Russian, and on the other hand Macedonian is close to Serbian (see: Пулевски 1974: 97).

This geographic link between Macedonia and Serbia has been a natural background for different relationships between the Macedonian and Serbian peoples, and it has influenced many important historical events in Macedonia ever since the middle ages. Not only during the medieval kingdom of the Nemanjići, but also for centuries afterwards, until the 18th century (see: Поп Атанасов 1989), predominant in Vardar Macedonia was the Serbian literary language of medieval type (the Serbian recension 1966 of the Church Slavic language). And after that period there were close cultural connections between Vardar Macedonia and Serbia. The orthographic reform of the Serb Vuk Karadžić, which offered a simplified graphic system, was very popular in Vardar Macedonia from the very beginning, which is confirmed by the shape of the contemporary graphic system of the Macedonian language. Serbian urban poetry was also well known in Macedonia during the 19th century (Поленаковиќ 1969). Of course, these influences from Serbian territory have even been intensified in the 20th century when Vardar Macedonia and Serbia took part in the same state, and when Serbian (once again?) became a language of prestige.

III.

The Macedonian geographic and linguistic position between two Slavic states, Bulgaria and Serbia, has caused in the past not only linguistic (see: Alexander 2000), but also political conflicts among the three sides. There is no consensus especially among the Macedonians and Bulgarians, about a series of important linguistic questions regarding the Macedonian language. Even today, for example, Macedonian is viewed in Bulgaria as one of the Bulgarian dialects (Български диалектен атлас... 2001), while on the other hand Macedonian dialectologists view the dialect of Bulgarian Pirin as a dialect of the Macedonian language.⁹ Although Macedonian is considered in Bulgaria as a 'regional norm' of Bulgarian (see: Единството на българския език... 1978: 14, 33), the Macedonian language and Macedonian publications are outlawed in Bulgaria today (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...).¹⁰ Taking part in this linguistic conflict there are also some foreign intellectuals, unfortunately sometimes not free of certain political inspirations - they

⁹ There are also citizens and emigrants from Bulgaria who "identify their native (Slavonic) language as Macedonian" (*Macedonian Language*: www.macedonia.co.uk/mcic...).

¹⁰ On the other hand, in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, between world wars, Macedonian literature was tolerated as "local dialectal folkloric form" (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...). This position enabled some continuum to Macedonian literature and culture.

usually act according to their personal attitude to the various nations of the Balkan, and lately especially to the latest civil war in Yugoslavia. Although the majority of foreign linguists do recognize the Macedonian identity (e.g. Friedman 1985, Friedman 1999), some of them discuss the matter from a Bulgarian point of view (e.g. Carmichael 2000),¹¹ while there are also foreign authors who observe this matter from a Serbian point of view (e.g. Stojanović 1997,¹² see also: Pajc 1918, Pajc 1998 [1928]³).

Theoretically, due to many linguistic similarities, the Macedonian people could have built their literary language together with the Bulgarian people (or they could just have accepted Bulgarian standard). The Macedonians could also have built their literary language together with the Serbian people (or simply accepted the Serbian standard), due to many rich cultural and linguistic interactions which have lasted for centuries, into this day.¹³ But historical circumstances in Vardar Macedonia have paved the third way to Macedonian people, and enabled them to establish their own state and to build their own literary language on the basis of one of the Macedonian dialects. The question what will happen in the future does not belong to science.

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¹¹ It's a very simplified, and even wrong approach that emphasizes: „As a language, Macedonian is very similar to Bulgarian, but historically, since Serbia has been a stronger and more aggressive state than Bulgaria [P.R.], Macedonia, and consequently its language, developed separately from Bulgaria, particularly since Macedonia's annexation by Serbia in 1912" (Carmichael 2000: 229). Macedonian "similarity" to Bulgarian (or Serbian) certainly doesn't mean that the Macedonians have to accept a Bulgarian (or Serbian) literary language. Situation after the disintegration of "Serbo-Croatian" language shows this very well. In addition, it would be a certainly controversial attitude to name as "aggressive" the state which was among victors in two world wars, differ to Bulgaria, for example. (About the last events in Yugoslavia history didn't say its last word yet.)

¹² An American professor of Macedonian origin, Trajan Stojanović, wrote that Macedonian literary language was just a result of political projections by Yugoslav Marxists (Stojanović 1997: 339).

¹³ Serbian cultural and linguistic presence in Vardar Macedonia, as could be expected, didn't stop after Macedonian separatism. Therefore, it caused claims among some linguists for some kind of Macedonian cultural isolation from the northern neighbour (Минова-Гуркова 2004).

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О МАКЕДОНСКОМ КЊИЖЕВНОМ ЈЕЗИКУ И ЊЕГОВОЈ ДИЈАЛЕКАТСКОЈ ОСНОВИ

Резиме

Иако македонски језик припада источној групи јужнословенских језика, он се у многим битним језичким одликама удалио од ове језичке групе. У томе је значајну улогу имао и сам географски положај македонске области, укључујући и њену упућеност на вардарско-моравску саобраћајницу. И након кодификације македонског језика, који је заснован на дијалекатској бази тзв. централних македонских говора (Прилеп - Битољ - Велес), довољно удаљених и од бугарских и од српских граничних говора, нису престали утицаји са севера. У том периоду македонска нација и даље живи у заједничкој држави са Србима и другим народима западно-јужнословенске гране. Ни коначним распадом СФР Југославије ови утицаји нису могли ишчилети, утолико пре што дијалекатски комплекс на северу СР Македоније генетски чини целину са говорима јужне и источне Србије. Главни град Скопље непосредно је изложен овој дијалекатској зони, што неизоставно оставља трагове у савременом македонском стандарду.

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